

AN ENVIRONMENT-FRIENDLY APPROACH FOR THE LARGE-SCALE PREPARATION OF ALIGNED MAT USING RECYCLED CARBON FIBER

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber-reinforced polymers (CFRPs) have been widely used in various fields, especially in aerospace industry, due to their superior properties in high strength-to-weight ratio, rigidity, corrosion-resistant, corrosion and fatigue, etc. However, the recycling and reusing of the used CFRPs with the increasing amount are still a big challenge for both academic and industrial areas. This work attempts to develop the approach for large-scale preparation of recycled carbon fiber continuous mat with controlled fiber alignment by using an unique aqueous solution through plate flow-induced alignment techniques. This kind of aqueous solution can fully disperse short carbon fibers uniformly and obtain a stable suspension. The fiber volume fraction in aligned mat reaches more than 85 %. It is found that the alignment degree of short carbon fiber in the mat is significantly affected by various factors, such as the viscosity of the solution and the outlet speed of the solution flow, etc. By optimizing these factors in the preparation process, the calculation basing on SEM images of the mat revealed that over 80 % of the fibers are aligned along the flow direction within the degree range of $\pm 15^\circ$. It is worth noting that the continuous aligned mat with 30-100 cm wide could be prepared stably and precised. The mechanical measurement shows that the aligned mat is an outstanding reinforcement for fabricating the high performance composites, which shows the great application potential in the polymer composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Short carbon fibers (SCFs) have been widely used in various fields, especially in construction and automotive industry, due to the combination of their superior properties in high strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion resistance, low cost, thermal stability and easy processability [1-5]. However, due to smooth surface, chemical inertness and inferior wettability, some obstacles such as poor dispersion in water-based solution have restrained SCFs for some further applications to some extent. At present, hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC), as a low-cost, eco-friendly and inexhaustible material, has been extensively studied as dispersant and thickening agent for some particles in water-based solution because the presence of the polar -OH group which could form hydrophobic faces to enhance the hydrophilicity of carbon fibers. However, very few research has addressed the dispersing mechanism of SCFs in water-based solution. In this work, HEC, as a dispersant, was utilized to enhance the dispersibility of SCFs in water-based solution. And the dispersing mechanism was also discussed from the chemical and hydromechanics standpoints.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Dispersion of SCFs and preparation of SCFs mats

A certain amount of SCFs with or without modification by dopamine were immersed into water containing different concentrations of HEC. And then, the mixture was strongly stirred by mechanical agitator for various times with different speeds.

The above well dispersed SCFs suspension was used to prepare SCFs mats by similar methods of papermaking process. The SCFs suspension carried by Teflon mesh belt removed some of water and HEC by vacuum suction and drying to obtain SCFs mats.

2.2 Characterization

The viscosity of liquid with a certain concentration of dispersant was measured by Brook field DV-III rotator viscometer (U.S.A.). The digital photos were obtained by digital camera. The surface of the aligned mat and the aligned state were measured and calculated with SEM. The fiber volume fraction in aligned mat was measured by Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Dispersion mechanism

The dispersion mechanism of SCFs in water can be explained based on the chemical and hydrodynamics theory. All parts within a particle suspended in a fluid under shear experience a maximum hydrodynamic force F and aggregation force (F_r) as shown Fig. 1. The hydrodynamic force is the resultant of the force (F_F) by flowing and the force (F_G) by velocity gradient. The F can be calculated by this formula: $F = \frac{5}{2} \pi R^2 \eta \dot{\gamma} \sin^2 \psi_0$ [13,14]. Where, η was the fluid viscosity; $\dot{\gamma}$ was the shear rate. And the aggregation force included the frictional force between fibers (f) and the surface tension of the hydrophobic effect (ft). Short carbon fibers could be well dispersed when the force F was bigger than F_r .

Fig. 1 Dispersion mechanism of SCFs dispersing in water using eco-friendly dispersant

Fig.2 The viscosity of water solution with various concentrations of HEC

Fig. 2 shows the viscosity of water increased with increasing the concentration of HEC. Based on the theory of hydrodynamics, the hydrodynamics force on SCFs increased with increasing the viscosity of water. SCFs could be dispersed well when the hydrodynamic force was greater than the sum of the frictional force between fibers and the surface tension of the hydrophobic effect. The dispersion ratio is lower when HEC concentration is less than 6g/L because the liquid has a relatively low viscosity and it can not produce enough shear force to separate carbon fibers. And the dispersion

ratio decreased slightly when the concentration of HEC is greater than 12 g/L. This is mainly because larger viscosity restrained the velocity of the liquid flow. Thus, the most desirable dispersion concentrations of HEC in water is about 6~12 g/L.

Fig.3 Contact angles of water on (a) SCFs, (b) SCFs/HEC

Fig. 3 shows the contact angles of water on (a) SCFs, (b) SCFs adsorbed HEC. It was seen from a to b that the contact angle decrease in turn. This result indicated the surface tension of the hydrophobic effect: $F_a > F_b$. This is because HEC could be adsorbed onto the surface of SCFs by hydrogen bond. And meanwhile, HEC adsorbed onto SCFs formed smooth membrane on the surface of SCFs which could decrease the frictional force between fibers. This result led to the decrease in the aggregation force of SCFs and promote the dispersion degree of SCFs in water.

3.2 The effect of layer number of spraying on short fiber alignment

Fig. 4 shows the effect of layer number of spraying on short fiber alignment. As shown in the optical images, well alignment of SCFs mats with more than about 85% fiber alignment within the direction of orientation $\pm 10^\circ$ had been obtained whether 1 layer or 4 layers. And the density of SCFs increased when the numbers of spray layer increased, but the alignment degree of SCFs decreased when the numbers of spray layer increased as shown in orientation tensor. When the number of spray layers increased the effectiveness of template decreased, leading to the rearrangement ability of SCFs decreased accordingly.

Fig. 4 The effect of layer number on alignment degree of SCFs mats

3.3 The effect of fiber length (l) on the alignment of SCFs

Regarding the effect of fiber length (l) on short fiber alignment, it has been studied with 2mm, 4mm, 6mm and 8mm fiber length and the results are shown in Fig. 5. The technical parameters for the dispersion and alignment of SCFs with different length was listed in Table 1. As can be seen, the dispersion and alignment of the SCFs with 2mm fiber length was much better than the same condition SCFs with 8mm fiber length. The longer the fiber was, the more difficult to disperse it in suspension.

It was difficult to disperse the aggregates for long fiber, and the alignment of SCFs with long fiber length was relatively poor accordingly.

3.4 The evaluation of the SCF aligned mats

The continuous SCFs aligned mats were prepared by the equipment as shown in Fig. 6. The length of SCFs aligned mats can be over 120 m. The carbon fiber content of aligned mats was measured by TGA and acid etching to be 85 wt.% and 90 wt.%, respectively. And it is seen from SEM and optical observation that the SCF alignment is well achieved, and the PAD is greater than 80.0% by calculation. The sample prepared by large-scale equipment reached the desired goal of our project. In the future, the optimization of process parameters will be conducted to obtain better alignment of fibers in the mat. Besides, the composites with aligned SCF will be prepared to validate the reinforcing effect of recycled carbon fiber.

Fig. 5 The effect of fiber length on alignment degree of SCFs mats

Fig. 6 The evaluation of the SCF aligned mats.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The dispersing mechanism could be explained from three main stages: At stage I, the adsorption of dispersant onto short carbon fibers processed which could increase F_v (viscous shear force) and meanwhile reduce F (frictional force between fibers) and f (the surface tension of the hydrophobic effect). At stage II, the individual SCF was ultimately separated when $F_v > F + f$. At final stage, the dispersed individual SCF would be maintained by steric hindrance. The most desirable dispersion concentrations of HEC in water is about 6~12 g/L. When the number of spray layers increased the effectiveness of template decreased, leading to the rearrangement ability of SCFs decreased accordingly. By optimizing these factors in the preparation process, the calculation basing on SEM images of the mat revealed that over 80 % of the fibers are aligned along the flow direction within the degree range of $\pm 15^\circ$.

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